

Insights from the Reproducibility Hackathon at the Swiss Reproducibility Conference 2024

Samuel Pawel (University of Zurich, SwissRN Academy), Peter Degen (University of Bern, SwissRN Academy), Gorka Fraga González (University of Zurich, SwissRN Academy, SwissRN ORD working group), Steffen Bollmann (University of Queensland, Neurodesk.org), Giulia Masoero (Swiss Ornithological Institute, Sempach, Switzerland), Quentin Guilloteau (University of Basel, Switzerland), Amira Asfar (Zurich University of Applied Sciences, Switzerland)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12516515>

The Swiss Reproducibility Conference 2024 (<https://www.reproducibility.ch/>) was an exciting event that brought together researchers from Switzerland and the rest of the world to discuss topics such as reproducibility, replication, transparency, open science, and meta-research. One of the highlights of the conference was the Reproducibility Hackathon (ReproHack), which took place on June 11, 2024 and was organized by Samuel Pawel and Peter Degen from the early career section of the Swiss Reproducibility Network – the SwissRN Academy (<https://www.swissrn.org/academy/>).

The ReproHack was a hands-on event in which 19 participants attempted to reproduce the results from published research papers with openly available code and data (event website: <https://www.reprohack.org/event/28/>). Five papers were kindly submitted by researchers from Swiss research institutions. It is important to emphasize that the ReproHack was in no way an attempt to criticize or discredit these research articles, but rather a way to provide constructive feedback to the authors and a valuable learning experience for participants. The ReproHack participants were researchers from different disciplines – such as computer science, psychology, ecology, or biology – and with different levels of expertise in computational reproducibility – from programming novices up to professional developers of reproducible research software. The atmosphere was lively and collaborative, with participants working in teams, freely sharing knowledge, and troubleshooting issues together.

Common challenges to reproducibility included unspecified software dependencies, missing or unclear documentation, inaccessibility of code or data repositories, and differing results due to differences in computer hardware. While no paper was perfectly reproducible, the teams made steady progress over the course of the event, were able to resolve several of the issues, and provided feedback to the authors of the papers. Some of these issues could be easily addressed by authors with additional metadata/documentation or revision of existing documentation. In other cases there might be some more challenging requirements to ensure reproducibility, e.g., setting up containers. At the end of the event, the teams presented the results of their reproduction attempts to the other participants and discussed problems and possible solutions. The post-event apéro with pizza and drinks was a perfect way to end the day, allowing participants to relax, share their experiences, and continue their discussions.

Overall, the ReproHack at the Swiss Reproducibility Conference 2024 was a great success. It fostered collaboration, led to new insights into computational reproducibility, and most importantly, it was a lot of fun. The SwissRN Academy looks forward to hosting more ReproHacks in the future. We thank SwissRN for sponsoring this event, the ReproHack Hub developers for providing infrastructure for reproducibility hackathons (<https://www.reprohack.org/>), the researchers who submitted their papers for reproduction, and the participants for their contributions.

